

COPIM

The promise of collaboration:
collective funding models
and the integration of
OA books into libraries

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Table of Contents

1.0 Executive summary	1
2.0 Introduction	1
2.1 Geographic scope	2
2.2. The perspectives of libraries	4
2.3. Building library relationships beyond existing ties	5
2.4 Futures of OA book publishing	6
3.0 Open Access books and libraries: key actors	7
3.1 OA book publishers	7
3.2 Libraries	9
3.3 Library membership programmes	11
3.4 Intermediaries	16
3.4.1 Knowledge Unlatched	17
3.4.2 TOME	21
3.5 Library consortia	24
4.0 Integrating OA books into libraries: challenges	25
4.1 Decreasing budgets and the effects of COVID-19	26
4.1.1 Major reductions in budgets over the short and medium term	27
4.1.2 Potential impacts on OA books	27
4.2 Uncertainty about external OA funding mechanisms	28
4.2.1 Uneven availability of library funds across the fiscal year	30
4.3 Incompatibility with collections development workflows	31
4.3.1 Incompatibilities with library management & acquisitions systems	31
4.3.2 Evaluating OA initiatives is workload intensive	33
4.3.3 Time consuming administration	34
4.3.4 Overly complex OA models	34
4.4 Doubts about credibility of OA publishers	34
4.4.1 Continuing prestige of legacy publishers	35
4.4.2 Career progression structures embed dominance of legacy publish publishers	35
4.4.3 Continued preference for printed books among AHSS staff	36
4.4.4 Lingering association of OA with 'predatory' publishing	37
4.5 Demonstrating value	37
4.5.1 Demonstrating global value	37
4.5.2 Demonstrating local value	38

4.5.3 More evidence needed for faculty to support OA	41
4.5.4 Quality of metrics	41
5.0 Building OA communities and support for OA in the academia	42
5.1 Developing collaborative OA offerings	42
5.2. Developing shared infrastructures	43
5.3 Raising awareness of OA among different stakeholders in universities	48
6.0 Towards a new relationship between OA book publishers and scholarly libraries	48
6.1 Objectives for the platform	49
6.2 Key principles for the platform	50
6.3 Conclusion	51
References	53
Appendix 1: Library Consortia in the UK	60
Appendix 2: Library Consortia in the US	70
Appendix 3 Critical information in deciding to support OA	74

1.0 Executive summary

This report identifies barriers for the more widespread adoption of Open Access (OA) monographs in the academy and outlines new ways in which OA publishers and academic libraries could work together to stimulate the production of OA books. It has drawn on feedback from stakeholders in the UK and US, gathered in a series of workshops, surveys and one-to-one interviews. Our research tackled such issues as the discoverability of OA content in library catalogues, the sustainability of OA monograph publishing, the difficulty of articulating the value of OA for supporting universities and the challenge of aligning OA values with those of stakeholders.

We also worked together with participating stakeholders to begin to reimagine a more diverse and inclusive system of scholarly communication in relation to OA monographs. Based on the conclusions of this research, we outline a proposal for a new OA model/platform that might transform the relationship between OA book publishers and libraries and boost the production and dissemination of OA monographs. We discuss the objectives of the proposed platform and its key organisational principles as well as benefits that the platform would bring for the OA monograph market and participating institutions. Finally, we describe a business model for the platform and examine possible challenges to its implementation.

2.0 Introduction

This report tackles a simple question: how can OA books be more successfully integrated into scholarly libraries? While there are some important practical efforts being made to address this question in a variety of different contexts, we explore the areas where further work is required to progress from a situation in which supporting and integrating OA books often remains a peripheral concern for libraries.

The report draws on a combination of interviews, workshop discussions and pre-workshop surveys with librarians and individuals involved in library consortia — a total of 44 individuals took part in this research, alongside desk research.¹ Although we cite most participants anonymously in the report, we do indicate if they have a UK-based (L-UK) or US-based (L-US) library role. We do name a small number of individuals who have other kinds of role, with their permission.

This data was collected as part of the ‘Community-led Open Publication Infrastructures for Monographs’ (COPIM) project.² This three-year project aims to develop a significantly enriched not-for-profit and open-source ecosystem for OA books. The report is one of the outputs of the work package: ‘Revenue infrastructures and management platform’. The aim of this part of the project is to develop new ways for OA publishers and libraries to work together, with the ultimate aim of improving the long-term financial sustainability of OA publishing. The recommendations that this report provides thus feed into this ongoing work.

2.1 Geographic scope

The report focuses on the challenge of OA publishing in the UK and US contexts. The focus on the UK is connected to some degree to the funder of the COPIM project – Research England, a UK-based funding council. COPIM project has been funded with a particular focus on the UK. The relevant context here is the widely anticipated move by

¹ Initially, we held three four-hour online workshops in a period spanning mid-May to early July 2020 in Cambridge, Michigan and Manchester. The workshops were titled ‘Library Support for OA Books’ and included 44 participants from the UK and the US representing 40 institutions and organisations. 23 participants work in university libraries, 9 participants work for library consortia, 12 participants represented publishing houses. In addition to this, 7 interviews were conducted with further representatives of libraries and library consortia, with 3 in the UK and 4 in the US. Additional input came from participants at a ‘COPIM Publishers Workshop’, which took place online on the 16th of March 2020, and featured academic publishers, scholarly communication experts and COPIM project participants, and which included a session focused on the Revenue Management work package.

² Further information on the COPIM project can be found on the [project website](#).

the umbrella organisation for UK research councils — UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) — to potentially mandate at least some form of OA for at least some scholarly books. This question has been consulted on as part of a wider review of OA (UKRI, 2020), although the COPIM project has raised explicit concerns about some of the directions this consultation may be heading (Adema, 2020; see also Barnes, 2020).

The US, meanwhile, is central to the future of OA academic books. It is the world's largest market for scholarly books. However, it features dominant academics cultures that present particular barriers to the widespread adoption of OA books. A recent survey showed that faculty in North American institutions were more sceptical about publishing books with an OA publisher than in any other region (Pyne et al., 2019, p. 14). The grounds for such scepticism are, however, very similar to those shared by many scholars irrespective of national context. This includes concerns about the perception of quality of OA publications, a lack of awareness and understanding about OA, and an understandable unwillingness to pay the high fees for publishing a book OA charged by some publishers — Book Processing Charges (BPCs) as they are known. These fees vary by publisher, with commercial publishers often charging over £10,000 to authors for a book to be available on a fully OA basis (UUK OA Monographs Group, 2019). One of the project's aims, therefore, is to address a national context in which OA books simultaneously have potentially the most to gain but also to challenge some of the most entrenched views.

It is important to be clear, however, that we, as authors and members of the wider COPIM project, do not see the solutions to the challenges of OA as pertaining only to these two countries. A truly enriched, not-for-profit and open-source ecosystem for OA books must extend well beyond the US and the UK. Many members of COPIM are part of the Radical OA collective, which has argued against versions of OA that are becoming entrenched in the global North and West (Radical OA, 2020; see also Knöchelmann,

2020) and for the need to nurture much more diverse, global cultures of knowledge (Adema & Moore, 2018).

With this in mind, the present report is intended to only represent an initial exploration of these issues, with work to investigate other national contexts already underway. A partnership between COPIM and the EU-funded OPERAS-P project has led to four more workshops in Germany (July 30) and Poland (August 13) as well as with stakeholders from the Nordic countries (September 30), and Southern Europe (October 08). The results of these workshops have been documented in a further [collection of workshop reports](#) and additionally informed a separate [scoping report](#) published in January 2021 by Agata Morka and Rupert Gatti.³ We are also in discussion with colleagues in other regions, with a view to thinking about how to respond to the needs of users elsewhere, for example in Latin America, Africa and Asia.

2.2. The perspectives of libraries

The report focuses primarily on the perspectives of libraries rather than publishers. COPIM is a project that is led in part by members of the [ScholarLed](#) consortium, which includes five OA publishers: [Mattering Press](#) (of which Joe Deville is an editor and trustee), [Meson Press](#), [Open Book Publishers](#), [Open Humanities Press](#), and [punctum books](#). This group was formed to explore the possibilities for OA publishing offered by collaboration and mutual support. It features presses that are led by academics and are often without access to formalised forms of institutional support. As a group, ScholarLed members understand well at least some of the challenges of integrating OA books into library collections from a publisher's perspective (see 3.1) — in part this is because some publishers in this group have themselves launched programmes of

³ This report focuses on libraries' engagement with OA books in 14 European countries. It examines general characteristics of library systems for e-content and OA publications, attitudes of library communities to Open Access, OA book policies and OA book funding, library/scholar-led OA book publishing initiatives, and integration of OA books in library systems.

library engagement. What is lacking, however, is a detailed understanding of how the offerings presented by OA book publishers are understood and assessed by libraries.

The views of academics on OA and OA book publishing are also largely beyond the scope of this report although these are clearly highly relevant to the futures of OA book publishing (but we discuss them briefly in section 4.4). In part this omission is because this is an issue that has been explored extensively, elsewhere (e.g., De Gruyter Open, 2016; Pyne et al., 2019; Stone & Marques, 2018). However, more importantly for the purposes of this report, it is our view that the better integration of OA book content into library collections is a vital part of the work that needs to be done in order for OA book publishing to become more stable, sustainable and attractive to academics. Without this effort, it will continue to be difficult for OA publishers to challenge the dominance of commercial, closed access publishers in a wide range of scholarly contexts.

2.3. Building library relationships beyond existing ties

This report is interested in how OA book publishers can engage with libraries *beyond* any particular institution to which they have a connection. In other words, how OA book publishers can form relationships with institutions to which they do not yet have any existing formal (or, indeed, informal) ties?

As a consequence, the report does not explore how OA publishers can better integrate with or emerge from a single library or higher education institution (see Adema & Schmidt, 2010). There are a number of publishers that can be looked towards as models for collaborating with libraries. ScholarLed member, punctum books, for example, is piloting a partnership with UC Santa Barbara library, while a number of OA university presses — sometimes referred to as New University Presses (NUPs) — depend on local library collaborations. Models in this respect include Cardiff University Press, Stockholm University Press, University of California Press, University of Michigan Press,

University of Ottawa Press (see Horava, 2016), and White Rose University Press (which is a collaboration between the Universities of Leeds, Sheffield and York).

2.4 Futures of OA book publishing

How OA publishers meet the challenges that they are presently confronting has the potential to play a significant role in shaping the future of OA book publishing, which in many ways stands at a crossroad (Deville et al., 2019).

There is a dizzying range of different business models used by OA book publishers (Adema & Stone, 2017; Ferwerda et al., 2017; Speicher et al., 2018; Penier et al., 2020). A particularly common source of revenue is the charging of fees or Book Processing Charges (BPCs). This is a source of revenue for publishers which many involved in the COPIM project are keen to avoid where possible, given its potential to exacerbate inequalities of different types. The ability to access funds to cover BPCs may, for example, potentially depend on the career stage of an academic (Pyne et al., 2019, p. 14) or their particular institutional and national context (Speicher et al., 2018).

Other sources of revenue include direct institutional support, direct sales (of print editions or other formats), subscriptions, and donations. However, only a few OA publishers (see 3.3) have succeeded in raising meaningful levels of revenue directly from libraries. More common are efforts by publishers to secure forms of library funding via intermediary consortial funding platforms, of which Knowledge Unlatched (KU) is the pioneer and dominant actor.

Existing routes for securing funding may in some cases hold some potential for OA book publishers, as we explore in the next section alongside introducing some other actors in this space. However, it is our contention that none of these funding routes at present fully meets the needs of a diverse OA book publishing landscape. Without new models for integrating OA books into university libraries, library support will remain an inaccessible resource for many publishers. This is despite libraries being frequently

identified as a key source of support for OA book publishers (Ferwerda et al., 2017, p. 114). Unless a way is found to more successfully integrate OA books into libraries, the reliance of many publishers on BPCs could become further entrenched. Our hope, however, is for a future of OA book publishing that is less reliant on author-facing fees and shaped by active collaboration between publishers and libraries. In that vision of the future, OA publishers and libraries are supported by open-source, non-commercial infrastructures able to meet diverse needs of scholarly communities.

3.0 Open Access books and libraries: key actors

In this section of the report, we will introduce some of the key actors that play, or could play, a role in the integration of OA books into libraries. We will also discuss some of the challenges associated with each set of actors.

3.1 OA book publishers

This report is associated with a research project which is led by members of the ScholarLed consortium of OA book publishers. Collectively ScholarLed, as a group, has a fairly clear understanding of some of the key challenges of engaging with libraries as seen from the perspective of a small to medium OA book publisher. Perhaps most relevant for the purposes of this report is the currently patchy understanding of library priorities amongst the group. While some ScholarLed members — notably Open Book Publishers and punctum books — have had some success in securing direct financial support from libraries (see 3.3), there is considerable room to better understand the context towards which current and potential future efforts will be directed. A significant aim of this report is to begin to address this issue.

There are, however, a number of other issues that, from the point of view of publishers, present potential barriers to the better integration of OA books into academic libraries. These include:

- **A lack of time and resource for outreach:** direct outreach to individual libraries is often beyond the scope of OA book publishers. Even for larger publishers in the group, where this task becomes more feasible, the labour involved is extensive and the rewards uncertain.
- **Variable levels of content production:** a library is unlikely to be interested in directly supporting a press that produces only a few books per year — even the largest publishers in the ScholarLed group produce more than 30 books annually each, which is a small number compared to the annual production of large commercial publishers.
- **The online availability of OA content:** it can be a challenge to explain to libraries why they should host and even fund content that is already openly available online, even if it might be valuable for staff and students to have this content listed in library catalogues.
- **Inaccessibility of platforms for integrating OA books into libraries:** many of the platforms preferred by libraries for hosting digital content are owned by large multinationals (e.g., EBSCO, ProQuest) which not only do not align with the values of many OA publishers, but also present practical and financial barriers to entry for small publishers (although Open Book Publishers' books are now available to libraries via EBSCO, see section 4.3.1).
- **Controversies around Knowledge Unlatched:** KU is the most immediately obvious route for OA publishers to engage with and secure funding from libraries. As will be explored in more detail shortly, this is an organisation that acts as a go-between between libraries and OA content providers, soliciting funding bids from libraries for particular books or collections of books, in order to then 'unlatch' these books once they are fully funded. However, ScholarLed members, who are committed to open infrastructures for the dissemination of academic knowledge,

have raised concerns about some of Knowledge Unlatched's practices and commercial aims (Barnes & Gatti, 2019; ScholarLed, 2019).

3.2 Libraries

The role of scholarly libraries is changing. Increasingly, libraries are shifting from a focus on acquiring content to acquiring access to content. On the one hand, this provides a potential route into libraries for OA providers, given the promise to deliver access to an increased range of materials at no or minimal cost. Discussions with librarians in our workshops showed that some libraries are becoming more aware of the political role that their budgets play and are taking steps to align their budgets more closely with their institutions' values. Some are also moving towards increasing community involvement and advocating for inter-library lending, resource sharing, and new forms of collaboration. Gregory Eow, president of the Center for Research Libraries in the US, suggested, in a reflection on the future of the scholarly monograph, that

at a big picture level, it means that research libraries at scale, university publishers, and scholarly societies [...] need to come together as three parts of the triangle and they need to work together.

On the other hand, as we have already argued, it can be time intensive for libraries to engage with OA initiatives (given that libraries are understaffed), and OA publishers struggle to integrate their content into commercial platforms that many libraries rely on to deliver access to users.

A key part of the contemporary publishing landscape is the increasing reliance among many librarians on so-called 'big deal' content packages sold by commercial publishers. Much of the discussion and debate around these deals has focused on journal packages and has been accelerated by the decision of some high-profile institutions to withdraw from certain deals (McKenzie, 2019). Less visible is the increasing move towards big

deals in book publishing, offered by vendors such as EBSCO and Ebrary (ProQuest) (Shapiro, 2016).

This relative lack of attention to the politics of book purchasing mirrors the decreasing focus on individual book acquisitions within many libraries. As Sharla Lair, Licensing Program Strategist at LYRASIS (a US-based membership organisation for scholarly libraries) put it, 'libraries [...] lost contact with the book, with publishing entities, because [...] it is easier for the library to acquire through aggregators'. One effect has been the increasing inability of many library staff to exercise their own judgement when it comes to acquisitions decisions, as compared to so-called patron driven acquisitions (PDAs) or demand driven acquisitions (DDA) (Shapiro, 2016). The rise of aggregators, and especially journal aggregators, within libraries to some extent mirrors the practices of the faculties that libraries serve, with journal publishing being dominant outside humanities and social sciences (HSS). As a consequence, however, there is a lesser focus on books within libraries and little direct engagement with small publishers. For example, a survey of 124 US institutions found that in 2017 journals accounted for 60% of total materials expenditure whereas monograph acquisition constituted only 25% of library budgets. The survey also revealed the dominance of commercial platforms for managing acquisitions, with GOBI Library Solutions (owned by EBSCO) being used for 69% of print book purchases and 86% of eBook purchases (Daniel et al., 2019).

The COVID-19 pandemic has had and will undoubtedly continue to have effects on library practices (see 4.1). In many institutions, the reduction in income caused by changing student numbers has affected and will continue to affect the future of acquisitions, with many libraries likely to experience cuts to their budgets.

The pandemic has also led to an increasing pressure to deliver digital material for students and scholars, as both teaching and research moves increasingly online. In this

sense, the unfolding effects of the COVID-19 pandemic have accelerated the shift towards digital content delivery that was already in progress.

3.3 Library membership programmes

One of the most common models of collaboration between libraries and open publishers that has emerged is the library membership programme. In the parallel world of journals, the most obvious example is [Open Library of Humanities](#)' Library Partnership Subsidy programme, which uses a banded library subsidy model to support an increasing number of gold OA humanities journals. It receives contributions from almost 300 members, raising around \$350,000 per year.⁴

A second example, even if not strictly a library membership programme given its focus on institutions more broadly, is the Institutional Membership programme run by [arXiv](#), an author-focused OA repository for articles across a number of scientific, mathematic, and quantitatively focused disciplines.⁵ It raises in the region of \$500,000 every year (arXiv, 2019) from banded membership fees from around 200 institutions (arXiv, 2018).

There are some similar schemes in the OA books landscape. Two ScholarLed publishers have such programmes: Open Book Publishers and punctum books. [Luminos](#) — which is University of California's OA monograph publishing arm — also offers a library membership programme, as well as Lever Press, which is an OA book publisher in the US connected with the [Oberlin Group](#), a library consortium representing 80 different institutions. Recently COPIM launched the [Opening the Future](#) platform in partnership with Central European University Press, and MIT Press announced a launch of a similar programme called [Direct to Open](#) (D2O). Although not a publisher, [OAPEN](#), in

⁴ Figures provided by OLH for the purposes of this report.

⁵ These are: physics, mathematics, computer science, quantitative biology, quantitative finance, statistics, electrical engineering and systems science, and economics.

collaboration with Knowledge Unlatched, also offers a membership programme associated with its books focused OAPEN Library.

Table 1 provides a summary of the five programmes focused on OA books, including direct benefits available to library members (Lever Press, 2020; OAPEN, 2020; Open Book Publishers, 2020; punctum books, 2020; University of California Press, 2020). It is worth noting, however, that some librarians make it explicit that the main incentives for libraries to participate are not direct benefits but rather shared values and goals. For example, punctum writes that library membership fees ‘help support the operations of a press that shares values with the research library community’ and ‘invest in a more diverse, scholar-led, community-owned, and not-for-profit publishing ecosystem’ (punctum books, 2020). Likewise, Lever Press’ membership offer provides few direct benefits but offers ‘membership in an advocacy collective that amplifies the voice of liberal arts institutions to ensure a future for academic publishing and scholarly communications that meet the needs of our constituents’ (Lever Press, 2020). The table shows that amongst the four publishers, the main commonality is a discount on print titles and, where they are charged, publisher fees. Three of the five organisations also provide both metadata feeds and usage statistics, with three offering some or all members the possibility of involvement in their advisory boards.

Table 1: Comparing direct benefits of library membership programmes: four OA book publishers & OAPEN Library

	Lever Press	Luminos	Open Book Publishers	punctum books	OAPEN Library
Annual Fee	\$500 - \$12,000 (<i>seven different membership bands, based on total library acquisitions budgets</i>)	\$1,000 - \$20,000+ (<i>different membership bands, providing different benefits</i>)	\$500 (<i>free if in an economically developing nation</i>)	\$500 - \$3,500 (<i>in the US, depending on institution type; fees in other countries vary</i>)	\$1230 - \$3075 (<i>tiered pricing depending on institution size</i>)
Number of members	56	28	174	16	16
Number of titles in catalogue	≈ 10	≈ 100	≈ 180	≈ 270	≈ 5,000
Location	USA	USA	UK	USA	Netherlands
<i>Member benefits</i>					
Usage statistics			X	X	X
Financial reports			X	X	
Reports on OA-relevant issues					X
Newsletters / email updates			X	X	
Free deposit service for member institutions' authors					X

Metadata feeds (e.g., ONIX, MARC)			X	X	X
Advisory board involvement	X	<i>X (for higher level members)</i>		X	
Discount on print titles		<i>X (50% for first 50 titles, except for members in the lowest band)</i>	<i>X (20%)</i>	<i>X (30%)</i>	
Discount on publisher fees	<i>(no BPCs)</i>	<i>X (10-30% off BPCs, varying by membership band)</i>	<i>X (no BPCs, but 20% off 'customised editions' fee)</i>	<i>(no BPCs)</i>	

The programmes differ in the membership-fee rate, the number of members and the size of their portfolio. There may be a relationship between the fee level and the number of potential members available. While, of course, the number of members a publisher secures is partly connected to the degree of outreach they are conducting, it is noteworthy that Open Book Publishers has both the lowest fees and the highest number of members (other publishers charge the same amount for libraries in the lowest band but charge more to those in higher bands).

It is also notable that there is no direct relationship between fees charged and the total number of titles in a particular collection. The OAPEN library provides access to more than ten times the number of titles of any of publishers, and yet its fee range is comparable. Luminos' fee structure, meanwhile, has the largest range, despite publishing fewer titles than some other publishers. And it has been successful at

attracting support within this full range: sixteen members, make contributions in its lowest band (\$1,000 - \$4,999), eight contribute in the second band (\$5,000 - \$9,999), three in the third band (\$10,000 - \$19,999), and one in the highest band (\$20,000+). This represents an impressive level of annual income from the programme, given Luminos' output. Lever Press' model is similarly effective: it has only 10 titles in its collection but has over 50 library members. This is one of the benefits of being a publisher associated with a library consortium: the consortium provides credibility to the press, a ready-made group of institutions to approach, via existing channels of communication.

What the variations between fee levels and uptake suggests, is that support from libraries — as both Lever Press and punctum advocate, and as many participants in our workshops also discussed — is likely in some cases not to be based on a simple cost-benefit analysis by supporting institutions, but on the desire within an institution to support OA initiatives because of the broader potential benefits to the scholarly community. The potential alignment between the values of OA publishers and academic libraries is, in the final analysis, likely to remain the prime selling point of library membership programmes. That is not to say that other benefits are meaningless: they are likely to often be vital for the credibility of a membership programme. However, it is the broader promise of OA that underpins them.

Being reliant on the indirect benefits of supporting OA is, however, a potential weakness of library membership programmes. In many cases, participation depends on the goodwill of institutions to support projects whose principal benefits may not be directly felt by that institution (which is connected to the 'free rider' problem such models inevitably generate — see Penier et al., 2020, p. 42). In fact, such programmes often depend on the goodwill of specific individuals, those in an institution who have the ability to mobilise institutional resources to support OA. This renders library membership programmes vulnerable to either changes in personnel or of financial

circumstances within an institution. In challenging financial times, librarians may have to face tougher questions about the direct value accrued to an institution by support for a particular OA initiative.

Additionally, library membership models face competition from other emerging models also based on the idea of libraries making regular contributions to release content in OA. One of them is subscribe-to-open model that so far has been predominantly used to facilitate transition of subscription journals to OA but could also potentially work in the book space, as we have argued elsewhere (Penier et al., 2020, p. 41-43). Under this model libraries also subscribe to get access, but the content is released only after subscriptions reach a certain threshold.

According to some of our respondents, the funds potentially available to support library membership programmes were also being squeezed by the rise of transformative agreements. These are agreements between libraries and publishers to turn subscription expenditures into funds to support Open Access publishing. As one of our respondents noted, mirroring a similar observation made by our COPIM colleague Martin Eve (2020), in some cases major commercial publishers are using transformative agreements as a way of increasing the total amount charged to libraries, by adding Open Access publishing costs on top of normal subscription costs. The effect, our respondent suggested, was to drain the pool of money available for supporting forms of Open Access outside of these agreements, including library membership programmes.

3.4 Intermediaries

Given the challenges of funding OA publishing, it is unsurprising to see the emergence of intermediaries facilitating interactions between libraries and publishers, acting as go-betweens among some of the various parties in the OA book publishing ecosystem.

3.4.1 Knowledge Unlatched

The most prominent intermediary is Knowledge Unlatched, which was formed in 2012 by Frances Pinter. At a conference in the same year, Pinter and her colleague Lucy Montgomery, made an argument about the importance of libraries for the future of OA book publishing, which was similar to the one made by this report. According to Pinter and Montgomery (2013):

[r]eal opportunities exist for publishers in a digital world and OA licensing will be an important part of sustainable publishing in the 21st century. Libraries have an important role to play in helping monograph publishing to make a successful transition towards effective digital business models that facilitate the widest possible access to scholarly books.

Knowledge Unlatched helps to better integrate OA books into libraries by acting as an intermediary between publishers and libraries. They have done this by creating a marketplace that allows publishers, in effect, to crowdfund titles with libraries as funders.

A simplified representation of the model, now known as 'KU Select', is shown in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1. The Knowledge Unlatched model, based on KU OpenEdition Select Webinar (<https://knowledgeunlatched.org/openedition/>)

The model operates according to annual funding cycles (the current cycle runs from September 2020 to October 2021). In these cycles, publishers are invited to submit to KU the titles they would like to be funded as part of a package that will be offered to libraries. Most titles are in HSS, although Knowledge Unlatched also offers two STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) collections that libraries can support (Knowledge Unlatched, 2020a).⁶ Submitted titles are then assessed by the Knowledge Unlatched Selection Committee, which is made up of around 180 librarians (Knowledge Unlatched, 2020b), with the view to creating packages to offer to libraries

⁶ In the current cycle, publishers have been asked to submit titles in a specific set of HSS disciplines in order to allow the creation of a 'relevant and coherent collection'; the disciplines are as follows: 'Anthropology and Development Studies, Communication, Cultural and Media Studies, Library and Information Management, English Language and Literature, History, Modern Languages and Linguistics, Politics and International Studies, Sociology' (Knowledge Unlatched, 2020g).

for potential funding. Libraries make pledges to Knowledge Unlatched based on titles/collections they wish to support, then Knowledge Unlatched creates a final list of titles that will be funded. Funds are transferred to the relevant publishers and titles are then ‘unlatched’ — published as OA texts, in other words. Both new and back catalogue titles can be put forward for potential ‘unlatching’ although the respective payments to publishers vary (in 2020 – \$9,735 for a frontlist title and \$2,212 for a backlist title).

To generate revenue, KU takes a 15% levy of the total amount by libraries.⁷ Knowledge Unlatched has, in many ways, been successful using this model – in the 2018 round, 283 libraries made pledges (Knowledge Unlatched, 2020c) with the 2019-2020 collection featuring books from more than 50 publishers (Knowledge Unlatched, 2020d). In 2018, KU generated revenues of over \$2.2million, with a profit of \$52,000 (Fund, 2019). In 2019, the equivalent figures, supplied by Sven Fund, the current KU Managing Director, were revenues of over \$2.7 million and a profit of almost \$19,000. Fund also highlighted that currently KU are working with over 100 publishers and 630 libraries worldwide, resulting in a cumulative total of 2,300 books and 50 journals being ‘unlatched’, and a net 2,36% profit margin (‘shared 50/50 with the non-profit entity Knowledge Unlatched Research’).

As this indicates, Knowledge Unlatched is a commercial organisation. This was not always the case: Frances Pinter originally established Knowledge Unlatched in the UK as a not-for-profit Community Interest Company. In 2016, key parts of Knowledge Unlatched were bought by Sven Fund, and the organisation was turned into a for-profit company registered in Germany (Knöchelmann, 2018; Poynder, 2018; ScholarLed, 2019). This generated some controversy in the OA community (see, for instance, Joy’s

⁷ This information, as well as the other details that follow, were provided by KU for the purposes of this report.

[2018a] comments), in part as there seemed to be a lack of transparency around the process.

Controversies have also arisen over some of Knowledge Unlatched's other projects — the [KU Open Funding](#) platform and its [Open Research Library](#) — namely some have argued that these represent attempts to monopolise and commercialise the infrastructures of open knowledge dissemination (Barnes & Gatti, 2019; Ernst, 2019; Gatti, 2018; ScholarLed, 2019). Another controversy arose around suggestions of conflicts of interest between Knowledge Unlatched and its parent company, fullstopp GMBH, in relation to a consultation on OA policy led by Research England on OA books, in which fullstopp was employed to lead part of the research (Knöchelmann, 2018).

In our workshops, surveys and interviews, KU received both positive and negative reviews.

On the positive side, KU is perceived as an ambitious central hub providing a large amount of varied content from reputable presses. Respondents were appreciative of the selection process that involves libraries (though some librarians felt that they still do not have enough influence on what happens on the platform). One of our interviewees remarked that KU (and SCOPE3) 'change[d] how [librarians] talk about [OA] [...] and gave [them] words, a new lexicon to use to talk about [OA]' [...] and a better understanding of what it was and what it could be'. KU is perceived as a reliable business partner and as a trustworthy recipient of funds, providing clear assurances around digital preservation and long-term access. Some respondents remarked that KU is good at responding to queries, and some valued the apparent transparency and sustainability of KU's business model. KU was praised for allowing libraries to easily convert funds from acquisition budgets to support OA and for its professionalism. Finally, a number of our respondents noted as a benefit that KU is helping to centralise funding opportunities.

On the negative side, some participants echoed the aforementioned critiques about what was seen as efforts by KU to ‘monetise OA movement’. One respondent claimed that a number of libraries had been disappointed when KU became a commercial organisation and feared that in the long run this might compromise the values of the OA movement. More generally, some thought that KU was too monograph focused and had many schemes, and that these were too aggressively marketed. Some respondents felt that KU has not been doing enough to help with production of new books. They maintained that paying traditional publishers to open their books is counterproductive as it is perpetuating ‘traditional book publishing’ rather than moving ‘the market towards sustainable publishing’ (L-US). In addition, some expressed disappointment with unclear governance and lack of transparency in the selection process (not clear which criteria the presses use in making books available for participation in KU programmes).

3.4.2 TOME

TOME (Toward an Open Monograph Ecosystem) is a US-based initiative, founded in 2017 as a pilot project run by [Association of American Universities \(AAU\)](#), [Association of Research Libraries \(ARL\)](#), and [Association of University Presses \(AUPresses\)](#). TOME’s key aim is

to change the landscape of scholarly book publishing in the humanities and social sciences by creating a broader and more equitable funding base for the high-quality scholarly publishing that sustains those disciplines (TOME, 2019a).

It involves a group of participating institutions — 14 initially, now 17 — who have committed to funding a defined number of OA monographs annually (the initial group

committed to three a year for five years; others have committed to different amounts), by providing grants of \$15,000 per book.

Authors at participating institutions can apply to their institution for access to this funding, according to rules and criteria specified by the latter. This funding can be used to cover book production costs at a number of participating university presses (66 at present, based both in the UK and the US). If the application is successful, this funding is usually paid by the institution direct to the publisher, in return for which publishers must commit to producing an OA version of the text, to be deposited in specified open repositories. Publishers remain free to produce a print edition and to sell it via their usual channels.

Given that funding applications by authors are dealt with by institutions, TOME is quite different from Knowledge Unlatched. It coordinates, streamlines, encourages, and promotes individual institutional efforts, acting neither as a financial intermediary, nor an intermediary between publishers and libraries (unless counting libraries at the author's own institution, given sometimes the TOME scheme is run through an institution's library). It is, nonetheless, an intermediary. It inserts itself

- between institutions, by bringing them together around a shared initiative and providing shared resources (e.g., sample contracts)
- between authors and institutions, by providing the former with a scheme that allows them to access funding from the latter
- between different authors, in efforts to forge the group identity of 'TOME author' (see, for example, the TOME author testimonials [TOME, 2019b]).

The TOME initiative is a significant investment in OA book publishing. The 14 initial participating institutions committed to fund 15 books each over a five-year period (3 per year). This marks a total investment of over \$3 million from US institutions. This is

also a potential issue with the scheme: the cost per institution in the pilot project is sizeable: \$225,000 for each of the initial 14 institutions. This is an investment that is likely far beyond the capacity of many institutions, based on the feedback from the librarians in our workshops. At this level, even committing to a single book per year would represent an investment of \$75,000 over a five-year period.

TOME also, at present at least, supports only one part of the scholarly publishing ecosystem – university presses, which are the ultimate destination for this sizeable block of funding. Independent and academic-led presses are not currently part of the initiative (nor are larger commercial presses). The programme also does little to challenge the BPC-focused model that the COPIM project is looking to help presses transition away from.

For those US-based respondents that were aware of TOME, there was broad support, with one respondent asserting that it represented a move towards partnership building and scholars' engagement in OA that could possibly transform publishing. As another participant put it (in a pre-workshop survey), libraries 'are not paying for OA or content; (they) are paying for the opportunity to create key conversations with authors and publishers for mutual learning' (L-US). Librarians also suggested that TOME helps provide opportunities to participate in conversations, obtain the know-how needed to increase their ability to influence campus leaders, to create faculty champions, and to evolve outreach and consulting programmes. Respondents also noted the potential for TOME to provide direct benefits to authors at the participating institutions, especially those working in niche subject areas and humanities. Finally, the relevant respondents appreciated the fact that TOME makes it easy for libraries to quantify and justify the impact of their investment, which is not always the case with other OA initiatives.

There were also a few more negative comments. There was some concern about the sustainability of the model, with one respondent noting that TOME gives preference to

rich institutions, big university presses and scholars who already have tenure. Another commented that they would like to see TOME focus more on developing OA infrastructures rather than on supporting individual books. That is why some participants thought the COVID-19 crisis will make it hard for provosts to continue to be involved in the programme.

3.5 Library consortia

Finally, library consortia may also have a key role to play in shaping new relationships between OA book publishers and scholarly libraries. The exact relationships that libraries have with consortia varies both between the UK and the US and within the UK and the US (in the UK, certain consortia are regional in focus, or focus on particular countries within the UK; in the US, consortia are often organised by states). However, common functions of library consortia include collective purchasing/acquisitions on behalf of libraries, assisting in the development of a library's services (e.g., provision of common software, training) and financial infrastructures.

The exact role of library consortia was not a major focus in our research with library staff although we have undertaken desk-based research to understand their particular role in the UK and US contexts; the results of this research are shown in Appendix 1 and Appendix 2 respectively. Nonetheless, we expect library consortia could be vitally important in shaping new relationships between OA book publishers and scholarly libraries. Areas of potential support and influence could include:

- Providing endorsements to new initiatives focused on improving the integration of OA books into scholarly libraries, as a way of generating trust in such initiatives
- Providing support in the management of financial flows between scholarly libraries and books-focused OA initiatives

- Providing advice and support around contractual issues in the relationships between scholarly libraries and books-focused OA initiatives
- Assisting with the marketing of new initiatives to members libraries.

4.0 Integrating OA books into libraries: challenges

Libraries face many challenges when supporting OA initiatives. These challenges include limited budgets, lack of decision-making power to develop collections and technical problems connected ‘with the practices of cataloguing and discovery’ of OA monographs (L-US). Those working in libraries, in various roles, not only have to persuade researchers to publish in OA venues; they also need to prove to the university leadership that OA is worth supporting financially. The latter task is particularly difficult because of the absence of any comprehensive metrics that could be used to simply articulate the value of OA.

Librarians⁸ in both the US and the UK also complain that despite making some headway in encouraging the adoption of Open Access publishing practices, they still have to confront what they see as misconceptions related to Open Access. One is that ‘publish[ing] digital scholarship’ will ‘reduce costs’ (L-US).⁹ The assumption of many colleagues in higher education is that the existence of digital OA digital monographs offers a route towards reducing overall expenditure on acquisitions. Another apparent misconception is connected to the problem of ‘free riding’ mentioned earlier (3.2). Again, some librarians report that colleagues involved in deciding library spending priorities object to paying for content that is already freely available online or to

⁸ We use the term to cover those working in a variety of different roles, including (but not limited to) acquisitions librarians, scholarly librarians, communications librarians, and library directors/managers. We will pull out distinctions between the views of different roles where relevant.

⁹ We use in-text abbreviations ‘L-UK’ and ‘L-US’ to indicate response from UK and US librarians respectively.

supporting OA initiatives that other similar institutions are not financially supporting, without taking account of the wider benefits such initiatives may deliver.

These issues provide some of the general context which feeds into the patchy support of OA book publishing by libraries and institutions in the US and UK. We will now proceed to explore in more detail some more specific challenges that were discussed by our participants.

4.1 Decreasing budgets and the effects of COVID-19

A strong theme in our workshops, in both the UK and the US, was concern amongst librarians about their budgets. Even before the COVID-19 crisis, many libraries were operating with tight budgets, with increasing pressure for OA initiatives to demonstrate their value to institutions. As one UK respondent put it, ‘the days of “it’s OA, let’s put some money to it” have gone out of the window years ago’. As we have argued in the report: *Revenue models for OA monographs* (Penier et al., 2020), this situation is being significantly exacerbated by the pandemic.

Thus far, the pandemic has led to several changes in the academy which may be shaping the context of Open Access publishing. First and most positively for the Open Access movement, Covid-19 has ‘highlighted the value of approaching science in an open way’ (UK library director, interview), in part because of the rapid shift to online learning in universities and the corresponding increased demand for digital resources. Librarians also raised concerns about their deals with commercial publishers and vendors and the need to see prices stay stable or even decrease, so that they can maintain their subscriptions. In the word of a US-based librarian: ‘[t]he global crisis initiated by COVID-19 is likely to accelerate a day of reckoning among scholarly book publishers [...] many publishers that have been holding on to the idea of ‘automating the past’ are likely to discover that time is up’ (L-US). More challenging for monograph publishing is the effect of financial constraints on budgets for books: there has been a suspension of

monograph approval plans in many libraries, even as the pandemic has triggered a rise of demand- or patron-driven acquisition for monographs.

4.1.1 Major reductions in budgets over the short and medium term

Libraries in the US and the UK expect that the pandemic will bring further significant cuts to their already shrinking budgets in the next 2-5 years along with possible workforce reductions. Specifically, our respondents report that they expect library budgets to decrease significantly – anything between 6% and 40% amongst our sample. The decrease might be caused, to a large extent, by expectations about significant drop in university incomes resulting from fewer enrolments and other cuts in income associated with the pandemic. Some participants expressed concern that their budgets may not bounce back for another 5 years. This context likely accounts for the fact that, in our survey, affordability, cost and value for money was seen as one of the two most important factors when deciding whether to support an OA publishing initiative (see *Figure 2* below).

One consequence is that many libraries – perhaps especially in the UK – are only supporting expenditure where relevance for academic staff and students can be clearly demonstrated. Some librarians expect that these unprecedented financial pressures may force them to cancel their library membership programmes. Likewise, a number of UK respondents anticipate reductions to their budgets for funding Article Processing Charges (APCs).

4.1.2 Potential impacts on OA books

This prognosis raises potential challenges for academic OA books. Academic books and monographs can be affected to a greater degree than journals because the latter are locked by subscription agreements that are unlikely to be cancelled immediately or completely. Even before the current economic downturn, librarians already struggled to provide funding the growing cost of supporting OA. Fees connected with APCs, BPCs,

CPCs (Chapter Processing Charges) and Digital Rights Management (DRM) were putting additional strain on library budgets which often do not have any monies ringfenced for supporting Open Access projects. Most of our respondents did not have ‘an institutional fund for OA publishing’ (L-UK) unless external funding has been secured. The growing publishing and subscription fees, particularly of ‘STEM content from the Big 5 publishers’, coupled with the costs of transformative agreements and ‘uncertainty of how to financially support OA, given traditional procurement processes’ (L-US) upheld librarians’ conviction that all these costs were unsustainable, even prior to COVID-19.

As argued earlier, tighter budgets will mean that librarians will be forced to focus more on their key activities, which is maintaining access to core collections and buying the content that academics and students need most. In other words, they may struggle to use the surplus from their collections’ development funds (if there is any) to sponsor OA publications or movements. If the library is not able to maintain access to the collections that have been available until now, justifying any Open Access expenditure will be difficult.

4.2 Uncertainty about external OA funding mechanisms

As we already pointed out, most libraries do not have any institutional funding ringfenced to support OA. Libraries therefore depend on external funding to finance their support for OA content.

UK libraries use the so-called OA block grants (OABG) from the UKRI that have been awarded since 2013. The OABGs are distributed on the basis of an algorithm, and research organisations (ROs), including universities, receive varying amounts of money each year – ‘the amount that each organisation receives is based on the staff effort on

grants'.¹⁰ These grants are usually administered by libraries and divided among qualifying researchers to pay Gold Open Access APCs.

In the United States, external funding mechanisms are even more disjointed. Librarians may receive allocations from their provosts or research offices, from external funders providing research grants or from their library consortia, but most of them draw funds from their materials and acquisition budgets. Allocations vary widely—from \$15,000 to over \$260,000 (McMillan et al. 2016). External funders that support OA include the Bill and Medina Gates Foundation (Chronos platform), the Simons Foundation and the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation.

Librarians from both the UK and US pointed out that there is a lot of uncertainty about external funding mechanisms for OA publishing caused by the scarcity of resources as well as inconsistencies in the approach to OA from funding bodies. Participants identified the lack of access to reliable and consistent funding as one of the biggest challenges they face.

As we have also pointed out in the COPIM 2020 report, *Revenue models for OA monographs*, seeking grants to subsidize OA publications is a very labour-intensive activity that has very low levels of success (Penier et al. 2020 p. 34). Moreover, as a result of COVID-19, public funds for research and innovation may become even less available. Funding organisations, particularly charities (examples include Cancer Research UK, British Heart Foundation, or the American Cancer Society, to name just a few) have already reported that they are in a much worse financial situation as a result of the economic recession. Fewer research grants also means less funds for OA research outputs. Librarians are worried about the impact of these developments on their

¹⁰ See Research Councils' OA Block Grants 2018-19 Frequently Asked Questions: <https://www.ukri.org/files/funding/oa/2018-19-block-grant-faqs-pdf/>

budgets and operations, as well as other pandemic-related economic uncertainties, such as inflation.

UK librarians were also concerned with changing policies of funders in relation to OA books, most notably the UKRI, the biggest funder of APCs. The concern was that if UKRI acknowledges BPCs as the norm in achieving Gold Open Access for books, echoing its approach with regards to APCs for journals, the move would further stretch library budgets. In most British universities the UKRI OABG is already insufficient to meet all of the requests for APC payments from potentially qualifying authors. Likewise in the US, many requests from researchers to fund APCs are denied because of lack of funds, with many libraries also having funding caps that, for instance, limit authors to one APC grant per year (McMillan et al. 2016). This being the case, covering much higher BPCs from existing OA funding sources seems challenging if not impossible.

4.2.1 Uneven availability of library funds across the fiscal year

A key challenge mentioned by both respondents in the UK and the US is that funds for OA are not evenly available across the year. Library budgets are drawn up annually and need to be balanced before the end of the fiscal year. One of our US respondents observed that there is little understanding among publishers about timescales for fiscal years and budgetary and procurement procedures at universities, the corollary of which is that librarians often receive requests for support after their budgets are already set.

Librarians have a narrow window of time to make critical decisions about how to assign external and internal funding. For some respondents, support for OA initiatives comes at the end of financial years, from funds that are left unspent. For other respondents, the key decision-making period is at the beginning of the financial year, a period in which negotiations are undertaken with various parties including faculty staff to determine their needs and those of their students. For those libraries, it is therefore in the first

semester of an academic year that they are most likely to be able to support OA initiatives.

4.3 Incompatibility with collections development workflows

Much of the content from OA book publishers sits outside the systems used by libraries to deliver content produced by commercial publishers to their users. The relative idiosyncrasy of OA content, combined with the related administrative complexity involved in integrating that content into libraries, remains a significant barrier for the integration of OA books into scholarly libraries.

4.3.1 Incompatibilities with library management & acquisitions systems

The incompatibility of OA monographs with library management systems, combined with patchy discoverability, remains a major stumbling block for potential library support. In the words of one American librarian, there is an urgent need for ‘[s]uperior OA content with superior records that work with library management system discovery software and optimize working with search engines like Google’ (L-US).

Another US respondent added that ‘library workflows have been designed to support the curation of paywalled content, and it can be challenging to integrate OA content into these workflows in a systematic way’ (L-US). For example, some of the metadata is not fully imported into library systems because it does not align with the formats that libraries use.

The quality of metadata provided is also uneven, with one US respondent reporting that they had to ‘vet’ OA publications to check accuracy and persistency of their URLs and the quality of MARC records (L-US). A number of respondents suggested that if OA publishers want to be taken more seriously, they need to be ‘as good’ as legacy publishers, with metadata a ‘cornerstone’ of OA collections (L-UK).

An interesting example of how these challenges are understood from a publisher's perspective was provided by Open Books Publishers in response to our query about their experience of integrating their content with the EBSCO platform (and similar platforms).

EBSCO has multiple platforms, each with its own submission process. So, for example, GOBI, which takes only printed works, requests that publishers send new titles in both hardback and paperback, for which they create their own metadata that will later be distributed to their library network. Another platform, EBSCOHost, provides publishers with a metadata template in .xlsx format, but the template does not request nor allow the input of information regarding the type of access or copyright/license of the titles. For publishers that can provide ebook metadata in ONIX 2.1, they do allow the input of information related to the license under which a work is published on the 'Audience Restriction' field. Similarly, EBSCO KB, a service used by libraries to manage collections and help with content discoverability, only allows the input of metadata that includes title, ISBN, URL, Author(s), Publisher, DOI, Edition/Volume Number and access type of the e-books, but not of metadata information related to the copyright/license of the title as a whole. This ultimately makes it more difficult for publishers to flag content as Open Access.

An additional problem is that the metadata that publishers provide sometimes differs from the metadata displayed in the catalogues of the institutions that obtain this information from these aggregators/distributors. Metadata aggregators/distributors sometimes input additional metadata (for the same titles for which the publishers provide their own) from other sources – DOAB, OAPEN, or JSTOR, for instance – which can result in multiple records being generated for the same title. In situations where libraries might decide to reduce the number of metadata records, this can result in them keeping only the records from these third-party sources/distributors instead of keeping those provided by the publishers. This ultimately means that the publishers' own

records are not displayed in the library catalogue. In other cases, OBP found that their records were displayed, but the links to these third-party sources/distributors were prioritized. This means that students and staff are often completely unaware that the publishers' titles are OA, as they most often access the prioritized third-party links instead of those provided by the publisher.

OBP runs a library scheme to help support their Open Access monograph publishing programme. Members of this library scheme are, for example, entitled to free downloads of EPUB and MOBI editions, for which OBP usually charges a small sum, in addition to the freely available PDF and HTML editions. However, this benefit is only available to members via the publisher's website. In cases where the metadata provided by third parties is prioritized, faculty and students are deprived of the benefits of the membership for which the library pays. The situation is also disadvantageous to OBP because it does not encourage readers to buy hard copies of books from their website, which is an important revenue stream for the publisher. Moreover, it hinders OBP's capacity to collect institutional and/or title-level readership data, which is key to demonstrate the value and global impact of Open Access publishing, both to the member libraries and to the wider world.

4.3.2 Evaluating OA initiatives is workload intensive

Librarians often remark that OA publishing market is very fragmented, with a 'multiplicity of collections' to consider' (L-UK). One US participant characterised the OA landscape as a 'crowded space without coordination' (L-US), with too many OA initiatives for librarians to evaluate and choose from. According to a US librarian: '[t]here are many, many avenues to support many small publishers in their efforts to publish OA – too many to track, evaluate, negotiate license terms with, and pay money to' (L-US). Libraries have 'too few resources, staff, time' to 'spend ages wading through everything; [they] just [want to] get straight to the details' (Caroline Mackay, Licensing Manager, Jisc). A consistent theme in our workshops was the desire for a more

centralised structure through which to coordinate and facilitate cooperation between libraries and OA stakeholders, a point to which we will return later (see 5.0 and 6.0).

4.3.3 Time consuming administration

Administering OA funding is also time-consuming, including potentially having to process invoices individually, with payment flows that do not integrate well with key institutional systems. A US participant, for example, expressed a desire for a more efficient workflow to avoid ‘additional transactions or split payment types’ (L-US). These issues become yet more complicated when OA compliance has to be factored in. As one UK respondent put it, ‘[t]he institution is required to put in large amounts of staffing resource to manage OA workflows and to monitor OA policy compliance. This requires large amounts of time and effort’ (L-UK).

4.3.4 Overly complex OA models

Some participants expressed uneasiness about the general complexity of OA deals, arrangements and business models, which participants variously described as ‘boutique’ (L-US) and ‘byzantine’ (L-UK). As we have written about elsewhere, it is indeed the case that the business models used to facilitate publication of OA academic monographs are even more elaborate than those for journals, with publishers often drawing on many different and complementary revenue streams that are available at any particular time (Penier et al. 2020 p. 4-5). These models are hard for librarians to understand, much less to explain to the university leadership.

4.4 Doubts about credibility of OA publishers

OA publishers continue to struggle for credibility amongst certain sections of the academic community whose support is crucial if the presses are to succeed. As one librarian has observed, when it comes to building collections and making choices about which initiatives to support, librarians are only proxies for research-active staff:

[i]t's not so much that we [librarians] want to be able to have control over the choice of publishers whose content is included in an initiative. We want to know that the publishers are the publishers our faculty members follow, both by reading their books and by publishing their own books. (L-US)

Therefore, it is vital for OA initiatives to be seen as reputable among a critical mass of researchers, which so far has not been easy.

4.4.1 Continuing prestige of legacy publishers

Our respondents suggest that the hesitation amongst researchers to publish their books in OA presses is in part connected to the continued prestige that some researchers attach to legacy publishers. As one librarian put it 'there is a perception of prestige with certain venues and that the goal is to publish in these particular venues' (L-UK). A UK librarian has pointed out that: '[a]cademic culture and practice in most disciplines remains very attached to the venue of publication', and the assumption is that there is a correlation between publishers' prestige and career success, as we argue in the next section. OA publishers, relatively new in the academic publishing industry, are still in the process of building their reputation, unlike established traditional publishers, many of whom are additionally supported by large marketing and public relations departments. This puts OA publishers, who are by comparison much smaller, at a disadvantage in relation to legacy and commercial publishers, given that prestige remains 'just such a big factor' for many research staff (L-UK).

4.4.2 Career progression structures embed dominance of legacy publishers

In the opinion of some of our respondents, the current system of rewarding research and career progression, which is often supported by both universities and funders, gives preference to established publishers and traditional academic presses. As one respondent put it, the system is 'monopolistic' (L-US), which means that even though

ever more funders insist on the outputs of publicly funded research to be published OA, this has not translated into larger copy-flows for OA publishers. For example, to quote from one of our UK-based survey participants: ‘OA for REF has been a stick rather than a carrot approach and I feel it has done little to make researchers think about alternative venues for their publications’ (L-UK). Another librarian remarked that PhD researchers and ECRs (early career researchers) are convinced about ‘the perceived importance to their academic career of getting their first monograph published with an established publisher and traditional print format’ (L-UK).

4.4.3 Continued preference for printed books among AHSS staff

Echoing the librarian quoted in the preceding section, a number of respondents highlighted the continuing attachment amongst many researchers for printed books and an indifference towards electronic editions as a reason for continued scepticism about OA. This is despite the fact that many OA publishers — and indeed all the OA publishers involved in the COPIM project — publish hard copies alongside eBooks. This trend is particularly conspicuous among AHSS (Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences) researchers, where the monograph is a core medium for the dissemination. One UK librarian suggested that AHSS disciplines are most likely to have ‘a low level of engagement ... with OA’ (L-UK), in part because OA texts are associated with eBooks. Another suggested that, in the UK, the ‘[a]cademic culture in some disciplines ... is very attached to the notion of the print book as a physical artefact and a creative object, and perceptions that this can't be appropriately replicated in an OA eBook’ (L-UK). This view was corroborated by a US participant who complained that their ‘humanities faculty ... dislike eBooks and insist that the library only buy print books’ (L-US). One UK librarian asserted that sometimes, these views can be connected to the income some academics (likely very few, more high-profile authors) generate from the sale of printed books.

4.4.4 Lingering association of OA with 'predatory' publishing

Some librarians promoting OA still have to grapple with the lingering perception that OA is 'an inferior publishing model dominated by predatory publishers' (L-US). This view, it should be noted, takes account neither of the robust and creative peer review processes that OA publishers have developed, nor the repeated calls amongst publishing scholars to nuance discussions of the diverse publishing practices that make up the publishing landscape beyond legacy publishers (see the various contributions to *Predatory Publishing* [Joy 2018b]).

4.5 Demonstrating value

Another challenge for many books-focused OA initiatives seeking funding is to demonstrate the value that they bring to both the scholarly community in general and to specific institutions in particular.

4.5.1 Demonstrating global value

According to some librarians, it would be easier for their institutions to commit to providing support for OA initiatives if they were able to provide persuasive evidence – qualitative and quantitative – that initiatives are 'actually making an impact on the scholarly communication landscape' (L-US). In this sense, the challenge for OA book publishers and other initiatives is to combat many of the preconceptions about OA publishing that have already been explored. More positively, publishers could also provide evidence of how OA helps to lower costs and could change patterns of scholarly dissemination, so it is more 'diverse, inclusive and equitable' (L-US).

Our research also provided some indications that the ability of OA book-focused initiatives to appeal to the broad scale 'global' benefits that OA publishing delivers may cut through in the US more than in the UK. This is implicit in the above two quotations, both of which are from US-based respondents. It also comes through in responses to our pre-workshop surveys (see Figure 2, below). None of the UK-based respondents agreed

that 'Alignment with mission (diversity, inclusion etc)' was a critical piece of information in deciding to support OA initiatives, whereas for US-based respondents it was one of the most critical pieces of information. Other forms of information that can be seen as related to an ability of OA initiatives to articulate its broadscale values were similarly rated as important more by US participants than by UK participants. This includes issues of 'good management/governance', having a 'sustainability plan', a 'transparent business model', and initiatives being 'multi-sided with potential ... to transform the market'.

4.5.2 Demonstrating local value

However, even amongst US institutions, respondents assert that a continuing challenge for OA initiatives is to demonstrate not just global value but also local value. That is, the evidence that the specific OA initiatives that their universities support deliver value for those universities. This includes demonstrating the value for research and teaching at the institution.

As noted, being able to demonstrate local value assumes particular importance in the UK, with activities that could demonstrate local value being consistently. That said, for both UK and US respondents, having 'content relevant for teaching and research' remains one of the most important pieces of information that OA initiatives can provide. 'Affordability, cost & value for money' is also crucial for both, even if it is unclear from the survey responses alone whether 'value for money' is understood as related to particular institutional priorities or as value to the broader scholarly community.

Figure 2: Critical information in deciding to support OA

4.5.3 More evidence needed for faculty to support OA

Some librarians also expressed a desire to be able to show that there is a ‘demand [for investment in OA] from institutionally affiliated researchers’ (L-US). That means, in practice, ‘support[ing] ... faculty in getting their publications to press more quickly’ (L-US) and making faculty’s research more available. Therefore, library-supported OA programmes must also make a difference on a micro scale within the university that is an OA sponsor. These more local outputs and outcomes might include course adoptions of OA books by faculty members or having faculty members among authors published in OA. As a US librarian put it, if large numbers of books are released in OA, librarians would like to ‘be confident that this would include [their] own researchers, even if [they] are supporting a much wider portfolio of content’ (L-US). These observations show that libraries are keen to show that they make most of their budgets and that they serve their own academic community well.

4.5.4 Quality of metrics

A UK-based participant suggested in our survey that budget constraints will make supporting OA initiatives very hard unless there are ‘deliverable impact metrics’ that showcase the value of the initiative for a potentially participating institution. Many librarians suggest they often lack the hard data to demonstrate the benefits of OA initiatives to senior management, especially in the current financially challenging times. Part of the challenge, some suggested, is that when data is shared by books-focused OA initiatives, it can be difficult to make sense of it (one mentioned, the data provided by KU, for example). In addition, there is, they suggest, no way to efficiently and reliably connect the usage of OA materials to members of their specific institution. Digital materials are often accessed from home (especially so during the Covid pandemic) and without connecting to a university’s VPN, which means that the IP address a publisher might collect would not be associated with a particular institution.

5.0 Building OA communities and support for OA in the academia

According to our respondents, there are several ways in which support for OA books could be increased within the academy. These include:

- raising awareness of OA among different stakeholders in universities
- finding new more sustainable revenues to support publishing of OA monographs
- creating new business models that would be compatible with universities and libraries' procurement processes
- encouraging universities to include pledges to support OA in their mission statements and strategies
- developing strong OA communities and infrastructures that include both academic and non-academic stakeholders.

In this section, we focus on three main areas of our discussions. These are (5.1) developing collaborative OA offerings, (5.2) developing shared infrastructures, (5.3) raising awareness of OA.

5.1 Developing collaborative OA offerings

A key theme in our discussion was the need to develop offerings that saw new collaborations between universities and OA publishers, including their various and varied representatives. A number of respondents asserted that the broader the community of stakeholders supporting OA programmes the better. These communities should involve not only librarians and publishers but also senior academic leaders, academic staff, students, authors, readers, and funders (Eve & Lockett, 2021). They should also be diverse – members of the community should represent all types of roles within stakeholders' institutions, from top management to subject librarians. There was also some concern amongst respondents from smaller institutions that their needs can get easily overlooked in such collaborative efforts. Any new initiative should therefore be aware of such issues and include representatives from a broad and representative range of educational institutions. As one US librarian participating in the American workshop put it '[c]ommunities are broader than the narrow academic communities'.

Our research also suggests some support, perhaps particularly in the US, for OA publishers collectivising. According to a US librarian: '[i]f OA book initiatives could get together and present a united front; more libraries would take notice'. Another librarian, also from the US, remarked that '[u]sing a central consortium fund to support OA over time brings more stability' and is preferable to 'pledging OA fiscal support across individual institution budgets over a period of time'. Another advantage of consortial models is that they could facilitate discovery 'because it is difficult for libraries to stay abreast and work on discovery' (L-US).

5.2. Developing shared infrastructures

One of the major objectives of our survey was not only to gauge librarians' support for consortial business models but also their thoughts on shared infrastructures. The concept of shared infrastructure has been gaining traction recently among some advocates of OA, even though, as we have contended earlier, achieving such a collective action may be extremely difficult due to 'competing and mutually exclusive interests' (L-US). For example, Brown et al. (2007) argued that adoption of 'a shared electronic publishing infrastructure across universities' can 'save costs, create scale, leverage expertise, innovate, unite the resources of the university (...) create a blended interlinked environment of free information, and provide a robust alternative to commercial competitors'. Collaborators can often produce resources, such as open-source publishing software or an alternative library integration platform.

Successful models of such collaboration, to give just a few examples, include Ubiquity Press, which runs infrastructure that is used by many presses in their 'partner network,' Lever Press operated by several US universities or the British White Rose University Press run jointly by the Universities of Leeds, Sheffield and York.

As we have pointed out in the *Revenue models* report (Penier et al. 2020 p. 39-40), business models that involve shared infrastructures are attractive because they encourage cooperation and help to minimise the forms of unproductive competition mentioned earlier. According to the authors of the OPERAS Business Models Working Group (2018)

[b]ringing together participants with a common interest is an excellent way of sharing services and infrastructure for the common good, of raising funds for a larger-scale collective project, or of bringing together stakeholders from different parts of the academy to find common solutions.

Shared infrastructure models help to distribute risks and resources among many institutions while at the same time making most of their know-how. They may also help to mitigate 'library fatigue' caused by multiple and uncoordinated OA initiatives or library membership schemes; fatigue that was clearly recognised by our respondents as one of key factors deterring librarians from engaging in OA programmes. Finally, it has been argued that shared infrastructure models can bring about economies of scale and help smaller non-commercial academic presses as well as new university presses embedded into modern university libraries to build brand and greater operational capacity.

The two charts below (Figure 3) illustrate librarians' expectations regarding shared infrastructure and issues connected with its ownership and governance. For both US- and UK-based participants taking part in the survey, the most important expectation was for the infrastructure to be publicly available, non-commercial and transparent. In the words of a US librarian 'Open Source ... would be easier to "sell" to campus IT, open governance would help sell to leadership' (L-US). There is a hope that that academic-led initiatives can play a role in challenging the consolidation of research infrastructure by commercial stakeholders (part of the context here is the purchase of Bepress, a development of software for scholarly dissemination, by Elsevier, and KU's transition from a not-for-profit to a for-profit company). Not-for-profit organisations are also seen as more likely to deliver transparency. As one of our respondents put it, only a non-profit status of the infrastructure can guarantee that 'open publishing [is] open to public scrutiny in all aspects' (L-UK).

Transparency is considered a prerequisite for establishing trust between different stakeholders. Many respondents emphasised the importance of open governance, that is transparency in the decision-making processes. As a UK survey participant put it '[i]t

would be essential to have transparency over the governance of such platforms in order to have confidence in them and in order to reassure our institution and our researchers that it is the right decision to engage with it'. A plea for transparency also extends to financial operations – business model, funding mechanisms, publishing costs and pricing. In the words of an American librarian (the US workshop) '[it] is vital to me that the economics and budgeting (along with governance procedures) be as clear and transparent as possible especially if the venture is approached to merge or be acquired by another entity'. A UK-based librarian noted that currently it is the lack of transparency in regard to publishing costs that makes APCs and BPCs unacceptable. Finally, transparency, as understood by the participants of our survey, involves data and privacy protection, editorial processes – submission and peer review policies.

To recapitulate, our participants suggest that successful OA initiatives must build inclusive communities, not-for-profit open-sources infrastructures with transparent governance and finances. In order to achieve this, they need to engage all stakeholder institutions empowered through trusted representation or direct participation. Finally, one US-based librarian mentioned the importance of ensuring that any financial commitments can be managed flexibly – as they put it: '[i]nfrastructures need to have an exit strategy too. No matter whether an infrastructure is commercial or open-source community-governed, we need to be able to exit when and if it no longer satisfies our local use cases. No system should be impossible to exit'.

Figure 3: Critical information in deciding to support OA – UK and US Respondents (more detailed data is available in Appendix 3) The respondents answered the question: 'How might the following factors (see the chart legend) influence you/your institution's decision to support such an infrastructure?'

UK Respondents

US Respondents

5.3 Raising awareness of OA among different stakeholders in universities

While the OA movement has come a long way in recent years, there remains much that can be done to raise awareness about the benefits of OA. The participants in our workshops believed that there is a continuing need for better education about OA across universities, including libraries, administrative departments, leadership, and academics. They suggest that information campaigns should not only mention the benefits that OA initiatives bring for the scholarly communication, but they should also educate authors about how OA can benefit them directly.

Swaying researchers to choose OA may require, according to our respondents, much effort. They think it is crucial for the success of OA that librarians play a key role in OA advocacy. For many, this will involve a continuation of work already being undertaken – educating and informing about OA, debunking myths about OA and pointing out the benefits that OA brings for the global scholarly community.

One survey response suggested that one area of particular focus should be liaising with early career researchers, who are currently most affected by the pressures and challenges connected with the transition of academic publishing to OA.

6.0 Towards a new relationship between OA book publishers and scholarly libraries

Our research has shown that those working in libraries often share many of the same goals as OA publishers. As a result, it seems that there is significant potential to strengthen relationships between libraries and publishers and to develop more meaningful forms of collaboration. This is a particular issue in the context of the ever-deepening corporatization of universities and scholarship, with libraries increasingly being considered as drains on university budgets. In this context, rallying support around OA and advocating for forms of scholarly communications that are more inclusive, diverse and equitable may help shift perceptions about the role of university libraries within higher education institutions.

Within the COPIM project, one of our contributions towards addressing such issues will be the development of a new content delivery model or an OA platform that will coordinate and facilitate collaboration between OA Book Publishers (OABPs) and Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). The platform will be designed keeping in mind the needs of different actors in the OA book publishing landscape (section 3), the very real challenges of producing OA books (section 4), and the possibilities for building genuinely diverse OA communities and for strengthening OA publishing more broadly, as suggested by our respondents (section 5).

By way of conclusion, we wanted to give a sense of how we currently see the objectives of this platform (6.1), the key principles that will inform its operation (6.2), before ending with some overall concluding thoughts (6.3). In due course, we will also publish further information about the business model for the platform, and how it will aim to be financially sustainable in the medium to long term.

6.1 Objectives for the platform

Our workshops explored what shape a potential alternative platform and/or model could take. Based on the insight we have gained from our respondents; we have distilled a set of objectives and principles which could inform initial development processes:

- 1) The platform should collectively facilitate OA book publishing. It should harness the specific potential of collaboration across OA publishers, as a way of collectively funding publishing via a non-BPC based approach.
- 2) The platform should strengthen relationships between libraries and publishers. We have repeatedly observed the significant gap that exists between libraries and publishers. In the workshops we organised, some participants noted that this was the first time they had had a direct interaction with an OA book publisher.
- 3) The platform should collectively educate about OA. It is vital that OA publishers contribute towards the work of educating scholars and management within HEIs

about the potential benefits of supporting OA not just financially but also through publishing choices and teaching.

- 4) A new model for OA book publishing cannot be based solely on the promise of funds being transferred from institutions to publishers. It needs to be supported by a robust funding mechanism that will make it sustainable in the long run.

6.2 Key principles for the platform

In order to meet these objectives, we have developed a set of principles that will shape the development of the new platform/model.

- 1) The platform/model should benefit participants. We recognise that it can be difficult for institutions to commit to supporting a new initiative without a track record. Therefore, the platform/model should be valuable for participants from the very start.
- 2) The platform/model should be guaranteed as non-profit and operate transparently. Several participants of the workshops recounted having been let down by previous OA initiatives that initially started as non-commercial ventures but then either became commercial themselves or were bought by commercial third parties. In order to generate trust, a non-for-profit organisational form and transparency should be enshrined in the governance of the new model/platform.
- 3) The platform/model should not be focused on individual titles. While retaining the flexibility for institutions to support individual OA initiatives, the platform/model should develop an approach that provides advice and guidance into the world of OA monographs and makes it easier for librarians to make informed decisions about which OA initiatives to support.
- 4) The platform/model should be simple for librarians and publishers to use. Usability will be key to the success of the platform/model. The platform should avoid over-complicating its offering, it should be as user-friendly as possible and should fit in with the existing infrastructures and workflows.

- 5) The platform should explore combining qualitative and quantitative data about the initiatives it supports, to potentially also include locally specific information to demonstrate to specific institutions the value of their support for OA initiatives.
- 6) The platform/model would benefit from support from local trusted partners. Many participants suggested that significant credibility would be gained by working with existing trusted organisations familiar in the local context. In our UK and US workshops, Jisc and LYRISIS respectively were seen as attractive potential partners.
- 7) The platform/model should be collaboratively governed by scholars, librarians and publishers; it should be responsive to the needs of its various stakeholders.
- 8) The platform/model should be flexible and expandable, both geographically and in terms of being future proof.
- 9) The platform/model should be open source.

6.3 Conclusion

As higher education institutions grapple with the wreckage that has been wrought by the Covid-19 pandemic, the need to support systems that foster a more equitable, sustainable, genuinely open scholarly publishing landscape is more urgent than ever. The COPIM project has a unique opportunity to intervene into scholarly publishing and to develop systems that will allow Open Access books to travel more easily between authors and their readers. As we have shown in this report, new collaborations between publishers and higher education institutions will be a vital part of this undertaking.

As a project, our next steps are to begin work on this new platform, in line with the objectives and principles we have sketched above. In keeping with the approach, we have developed so far, this work will be open, and it will be collaborative. In that respect, this scoping report provides an initial roadmap for our work that will be added to in the coming months and years.

We would also like to extend some invitations. To those librarians looking to support Open Access books, please do get in touch, so we can work to develop solutions that meet your needs and those whom you represent. Similarly, we also invite Open Access book publishers and other OA-book focused initiatives to reach out to us. The challenges of OA book publishing cannot be solved by any one organisation. COPIM as a project emerged as part of a commitment between organisations to work collaboratively rather than competitively. With this in mind, we look forward to others joining us to explore the potential of scaling collaboration (Adema & Moore, 2021) and for, ultimately, reshaping what it means to publish a scholarly book Open Access.

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Appendix 1: Library Consortia in the UK

Libraries in the UK make acquisitions to their collections in three ways: 1) individually through institutional deals, 2) through the regional consortia they belong to, 3) via Jisc (directly or indirectly through their regional consortium). In addition to using regional consortia or Jisc, many English libraries purchase material through Southern Universities Purchasing Consortium (SUPC), which is one of the largest purchasing consortia in England. In Scotland, academic and research libraries collectively purchase materials through the Scottish Confederation of University and Research Libraries (SCURL) and the Scottish Higher Education Digital Library (SHEDL). The latter was launched in 2009 to facilitate access to electronic content for the users of the SCURL. SHEDL negotiates joint licensing of publisher resources. Currently it holds 12 licensing contracts that provide access to over 3,000 journals and 60,000 eBooks (ICOLC, n.d. Scottish Higher Education Digital Library). Scottish libraries also use Jisc for material that is not supported by SCURL or SHEDL.

The above organisations and smaller regional consortia offer collaborative service development for their members. They provide customer service, common software and other resources, and what is most important, their procurement teams use collective bargaining power to purchase competitively priced goods and services from various university, college and library suppliers. Their main objective is to reduce procurement costs (monetary or temporal), bolster delivery services for members, design and deliver training courses for staff and help with inter-library (ILL) loans. Their websites usually mention OA as part of their core organisational values.

Consortium	Aims
RLUK, Jisc, SCONUL, SCURL	Promotion of Open Scholarship/OA
M25, RLUK, NoWal, SCONUL, WHELF, Northern Collaboration, UKUPC, SCURL, M25, Jisc	Advancing quality of research, services and resources
NoWAL, WHELF, Northern Collaboration, RLUK, M25, Jisc, SCONUL	Staff training courses and development
NoWAL, UKUPC, WHELF, M25	Facilitating access and borrowing policy

NoWAL, SCURL , WHELF, NeYal , UKUPC, RLUK	Purchasing materials
SCONUL, WHELF, SCURL, Northern Collaboration, RLUK, M25	Promotion of best practices and policies
SCONUL, WHELF, RLUK, Jisc	Provision of quantitative data
Northern Collaboration, UKUPC, Jisc, WHELF	Assistance with technology
UKUPC, Jisc	Sharing agreements

Purchasing Consortia

There are eight regional and specialist purchasing consortia in England, Scotland and Wales that work under the umbrella of UK University Purchasing Consortia (UKUPC). They include 1) Higher Education Purchasing Consortium (HEPCW) in Wales, 2) APUC Advanced Procurement for Universities and Colleges (APUC) in Scotland, 3) Southern Universities Purchasing Consortium (SUPC), 4) London Universities Purchasing Consortium (LUPC), 5) North Eastern Universities Purchasing Consortium (NEUPC), 6) North Western Universities Purchasing Consortium (NWUPC), 7) the Energy Consortium (TEC), and 8) the University Caterers Organization (TUCO). UKUPC's goal is 'achieving financial and operational efficiencies, as well as sharing best practice [and ...] increasing our teams' skills and capabilities which in turn benefits our members' (UKUPC n.d.). In 2018-19, UKUPC generated £87.3 million cashable savings and £79.1 non-cashable savings (UKUPC 2020).

How do regional consortia work?

All regional consortia operate in the same way. For example, the mentioned earlier SUPC manages procurement and transactions and collects data for its 139 library members. It liaises with subscription agents and suppliers and has no direct relations with publishers. Their mission is '[t]o deliver a comprehensive set of high-quality procurement services that add tangible value to the members and the education sector as a whole' (SUPC, n.d. About SUPC).

At the moment, SUPC operates two library framework agreements, one for periodicals and one for books/eBooks. Framework agreements last from 2 to 4 years. SUPC tries to

make sure their suppliers put no barriers to OA materials. All English and Welsh universities can join these agreements. According to SUPC, their role is not only to provide good value for money in procurement processes but also to add value 'for the sector ... by supporting OA approaches or supporting improvements in metadata or accessibility. It is often about finding alignment with other bodies' (Gavin Phillips).

SUPC's frameworks are compliant with the public sector and EU procurement regulations, so they always involve invitations to tendered to shortlist the best suppliers. This means that SUPC advertises all upcoming tender opportunities in line with Public Contracts Regulations (PCR) requirements. Those suppliers who best meet the tender requirements of high-quality products/services are awarded tenders and listed as suppliers on SUPC agreements, but SUPC members are entirely independent in their purchasing decisions and are not obliged to use SUPC agreements. UK University Purchasing Consortia and its members are committed to supporting and promoting responsible procurement, which means 'ensuring that [they] implement procedures and policies to support the elimination of human rights abuses in the supply chain, the removal of barriers for SMEs, the promotion of social value in tenders, and the protection of the environment' (SUPC, N.d. Responsible procurement).

Jisc

Jisc is a UK HE and skills sector not-for-profit organization for digital services and solutions. Jisc operates shared digital infrastructures such as the JANET, eduroam UK, Library Hub, the Archives Hub (a catalogue of the collections of academic and other institutions), Sherpa (tools for checking permissions around OA), Learner Analytics and authentication systems (Open Athens and the UK Federation). It offers advice on digital technology for education and procurement consulting for universities, colleges and learning providers. As an intermediary, Jisc negotiates with commercial publishers and IT vendors to get better deals for the UK higher, further education and skill sector.

In 2019-20 Jisc helped its members to save £189m. According to Jisc's website, 'Jisc's negotiations have contained annual prices increases for electronic journal packages to

2.25% for HE and 1% for FE, compared to the market average of 4-5%' (Jisc, n.d. Savings and value).

Jisc operates as a national body. It is funded by UK further and HE funding bodies, and higher education institutions via membership subscriptions. Jisc uses a banding system to determine the rate of subscription. Bands are allocated to every organisation that uses Jisc negotiation and licensing service.

Jisc licensing team negotiate frameworks, that is 'umbrella' agreements, at the national level on behalf of the consortium, saving the members duplicated effort from negotiating individually. Jisc procurement team runs DPS – a dynamic purchasing system – to contract works, services and goods for the sector. Jisc establishes a pool of publishers/suppliers, and then libraries/consortia browse, purchase or license whatever they want from this pool via Jisc Collections agreements and licence subscriptions manager.

Jisc also offer assistance in procuring OA systems, such as institutional repositories.

National Consortia

- **The Society of College, National and University Libraries (SCONUL)** is the largest consortium in the UK (182 members). It represents all the university libraries in the UK and Ireland. It aims to promote awareness of the role of academic libraries in supporting research excellence and student achievement and employability, and represents their views and interests to government, regulators and other stakeholders. It helps member libraries collaborate to deliver services efficiently, including through shared services, and to share knowledge and best practice.
- **Research Libraries United Kingdom (RLUK)** consortium (37 members) aims to advance and help increase the impact of research.

Regional Consortia

England

- **Northern Collaboration** consortium (29 HE library members which must be members of SCONUL) aims to provide a framework so libraries can collectively improve their services, increase efficiency and explore new business models. In addition, it aims to enhance communication among librarians, raise awareness of new developments.
- **North West Academic Libraries (NoWAL)** consortium (14 members with UK Universities and Colleges of HE libraries in Cheshire, Cumbria, Greater Manchester, Lancashire and Merseyside) is a subgroup of SCONUL. It aims to strengthen the collaboration and share services among its members as well as be the regional voice of SCONUL.
- **North East Yorkshire Libraries (NEYAL)** consortium is a collaboration of academic libraries (24 members) whose purpose is to purchase library materials and services to support teaching, learning and research at the most advantageous prices for the Consortium.
- **M25 consortium** (55 members) aims exclusively at providing library services training. It offers one stop access to the library catalogues of nearly 60 world-renowned institutions and specialist collections within the M25 Consortium of Academic Libraries — helping them obtain resources from across London and the South-East within the M25 region (Greater London) and more widely across the East and Southeast.

Scotland

- **Scottish Confederation of University and Research Libraries (SCURL)** includes the main HE institutions in Scotland and organises a number of activities from training to purchasing materials. SCURL recently commissioned research to see if it would be possible to set up a Scottish universities OA press. The results, published in August 2019 (SCURL 2019) were positive, but it is not clear if this project will go ahead.

Wales

- **Wales Higher Education Libraries Forum (WHELF)** has 14 members. Its mission is 'to promote library and information services co-operation, to encourage the exchange of ideas, to provide a forum for mutual support and to help facilitate new initiatives in library and information service provision' (WHELF 2021).

Country	Consortium	Members	Membership Cost
UK & Ireland	Society of College, National and University Libraries (SCONUL)	182	No fee
United Kingdom	Research Libraries United Kingdom (RLUK)	37	Subscription rate determined annually by the Board of Directors
England	Northern Collaboration	29	Based on Jisc bands (£375 to £938/year)
	North West Academic Libraries (NoWAL)	14	Annual subscription charges are agreed by the Operations Group, following options provided by the Treasurer, and recommendations made to the Board at the June meeting and AGM. Subscriptions are based on Jisc bands.
	North East Yorkshire Libraries (NEYAL)	24	Annual subscription, the amount is determined by the Steering Committee and reviewed annually
	M25	55	Rate and method of calculating subscriptions is agreed annually at the Consortium's Annual General Meeting.
	Midlands Universities Academic Libraries (MUAL)	No information	No information
Scotland	SCURL	All Scottish HEI and research libraries, the two major public reference libraries in Glasgow and Edinburgh, the National Library of Scotland, National Museums Scotland, the Open University and the Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh.	No information
Wales	Wales Higher Education Libraries Forum (WHELP)	14	No information
Ireland	Northern Ireland Academic Libraries Consortium	No information	No information

Consortium	Acquisitions	OA	Working Groups
RLUK		Strategy for 2018/21 focuses on Open Scholarship and a collective approach.	RLUK's OA Publisher Processes Group (OAPP) OAPP focuses on the challenges, barriers, and other issues in relation to OA practice and processes. External: Jisc OA Stakeholders Group OA Monographs Steering Group Jisc-Elsevier Open Science Group
NoWAL			Procurement Group (purchasing monographs and serials)
SCONUL		Strategy 2019-22 themes are around content a) budget constraints and the libraries' broader role b) operating in a hybrid world c) the cost of content: changing the model	The Content Strategy Group, member of the UUK OA Coordination group and its sub-groups, which argue for reforms to speed the transition to OA in the UK. During 2018 SCONUL produced briefings for members on key issues for academic libraries, including on the extensive developments of OA policy, which occurred during 2018. They held a Content Forum meeting on OA policies to provide members with a first-hand account from those involved in developing the policy.
SCURL		SCURL is currently scoping the development of an OA publishing platform to be operated by Scottish university libraries.	

Northern Collaboration			Potential projects currently under consideration: 'OA publishing/libraries as publishers' and 'Students as researchers'
Jisc	Negotiating OA agreement: Jisc Collections worked with Springer to develop its first transformative agreement and is currently negotiating with all the major publishers. Throughout 2019 they have also invested in ensuring learned society publishers have the opportunity to work with Jisc to offer transformative agreements to the UK higher education sector. This has resulted in five pilot 'read and publish' for 2020, many more are in the pipeline for 2021	Jisc supports transition to OA through negotiating agreements that meet Plan S and research funders' policies – and require the adoption of standards and service levels in those agreements. Policy and engagement: they do not have a policy position on how to achieve OA. Their work is informed by the evidence of benefit to UK research, wider economy and society. They are active in many OA groups. They participate in Universities-UK OA coordinating group. It brings together publishers, learned societies, universities, libraries, managers, funders and other.	They work with the Universities-UK OA coordinating group, which is the main body the UK government looks to in relation to OA
SCURL			SCURL is presently considering developing an OA publishing platform that will be operated by Scottish University libraries

Appendix 2: Library Consortia in the US

Consortia in the US come in different types and sizes. There are no national consortia that play an equivalent role to Jisc in the UK. Bostick (2001) provides a good overview of US consortia and explains the long tradition of library consortia. Consortia can be organised around a specific type of libraries or combine different types. When a consortium has different types of libraries it is called multitype. State libraries also form consortia that include different types of libraries, such as Swan Libraries and RAILS. Larger consortia include libraries of more than one state that are either close geographically (such as Amigos) or cover many states such as LYRASIS. Libraries in the US tend to belong to multiple consortia and networks. Consortia can also include private institutions, public or both.

Multi state consortia

LYRASIS

LYRASIS is a multi-state consortium. It has more than 1,000 members in different states and was created from the consolidation of Solinet and Palinet consortia. In 2019 they also merged with DuraSpace, an initiative that provides open-source software. LYRASIS provides different services for its members. It supports open-source technologies, helps with content creation and acquisition, consultation, fiscal services in organisations such as libraries, archives, museums.

It partners with vendors to provide products and services with better prices and terms to its members. It has a central model license approach to simplify the admin processes for licensing content and provide discounts.

Center for Research Libraries (CRL)

The Center for Research Libraries (CRL) is an international multi-consortium. It supports original research and teaching in Humanities and Social Sciences. It preserves and makes available resources built by the member libraries. It has a strong focus on preservation and sharing specialised material.

What is unique about CRL is that it works as a library, but in terms of governance and business model, it is like a consortium.

Association of Research Libraries (ARL)

The Association of Research Libraries (ARL) includes libraries and archives from the US and Canada. Members are deans and directors of libraries. It advocates on behalf of their members, shares intelligence on current issues and helps members leverage technology. It also participates in conversations around policies. ARL aims to advance research, learning and scholarly communication. It fosters open exchange of ideas and helps make partnerships between libraries.

Big 10 Academic Alliance

The Big Ten Academic Alliance Consortium is the collaboration of 14 universities. It aims to share expertise, resources and collaborate on innovative projects. The member libraries have collaborative purchasing and licensing programmes that help universities negotiate better terms. They benefit through common strategic sourcing initiatives, identifying strategies to handle emerging issues and implementing best practices. It is governed and funded by the provosts of the member universities.

Amigos Library Services Consortium

Amigos Library Services Consortium is one of the largest library service networks in US counting 524 members. It provides member discounts, training, admin and fiscal services by hosting events or conferences. It negotiates vendor discounts on libraries' behalf and sponsors agreements among members for borrowing material.

Waldo

Waldo has more than 600 members and aims to support procurement and administration of electronic information services. It provides support with technology: database trials, IP address management. It helps with competitive consortial procurement.

Consortium	Aim
LYRASIS, CRL, ARL, Big 10 Academic Alliance	Open Scholarship/OA
LYRASIS, CRL, Big 10 Academic Alliance, Amigos Library Services, Waldo	Advance quality research services and resources
LYRASIS, CRL, ARL, Big 10 Academic Alliance, Amigos Library Services, Waldo	Staff training courses/ development
LYRASIS, CRL, ARL, Big 10 Academic Alliance, Amigos Library Services	Access and borrowing policy
LYRASIS, CRL, Big 10 Academic Alliance, Amigos Library Services, Waldo	Purchasing materials
LYRASIS, Big 10 Academic Alliance	Sharing best practices/ policies
ARL, Big 10 Academic Alliance	Statistics
LYRASIS, Amigos Library Services, Waldo	Assistance with technology/share software
LYRASIS, CRL, Amigos Library Services, Waldo	Sharing agreements

Consortium	Members	Membership Cost
LYRASIS	<1000	Based on Tiers (from \$0-\$2,500)
CRL	<200	Based on type of membership ranges from \$1,200-\$78,000
ARL	124	
Big 10 Academic Alliance	14	
Amigos Library Services	524	Fees are determined by library type and annual budget

Consortium	Acquisitions	OA
LYRASIS	Extended their role beyond licensing and negotiating discounts and partnered with many OA initiatives	LYRASIS and its think tank, Leaders Circle, conduct research on scholarly publishing to understand how institutions support dissemination and OA. It has a role as US national contact point for the following initiatives: SCOAP ³ US, Knowledge Unlatched, and Open Library of Humanities.
ARL		Through collective action they work to increase the amount of high-quality scholarship that is openly available to position their members as leaders on 'open

		<p>science by design' within their own institutions and to provide leadership on high-impact collective collections initiatives. The Association partnered nationally and internationally to inform open science practice. The Association is committed to advancing open monographs as part of a movement to sustain the infrastructure of academy-based humanities and social sciences publishing. AAU, ARL, and the Association of University Presses (AUPresses) launched openmonographs.org to flip the funding model for university publishing.</p>
Big 10 Academic Alliance		<p>In 2006, the Provosts of the Big Ten Academic Alliance publicly endorsed congressional passage of federal legislation (Federal Research Public Access Act) that would mandate deposit of federally funded research findings letter in an openly accessible repository. They promote author control over the dissemination of their research. They manage secure repositories for OA content.</p>

State Consortia

- **Swan Libraries:** has 97 members in Chicago. It aims to share and give access to resources and support library staff with IT, consulting, training. The members share a catalogue, cataloguing services, unique collection of materials.
- **RAILS:** has approximately 1,300 academic, public, school, and special library agencies in northern and west-central Illinois. It offers different services, such as ILL, shared catalogue, cooperative purchasing. It helps with training.
- **Triangle Research Libraries Network:** is a collaboration of four universities in North Carolina. It aims to help with the financial, human and information resources through cooperative efforts to help with research and teaching. They share collections, collaborative digital materials, knowledge, and training.
- **Michigan Library Consortium:** facilitates sharing resources and collaborates with organisations to benefit Indiana and Michigan libraries. The members share best practices, create communities and benefit from networking. They also purchase and share resource services.

- **OhioLink:** has 117 members in Ohio. It is a multi-consortium. It cooperatively acquires, provides access to and preserves print and digital resources to advance research and teaching in Ohio.
- **California Digital Library (CDL):** is a coalition of 10 University of California libraries. It provides library services through campus partnerships with external collaborations to help libraries have high impact, support scholarship and share resources. It has members that represent administration, technology and leadership of the campuses. The campuses help with discovery, collections development and management, publishing and digitisations. They offer business services, information services, infrastructure and applications support services, and user-experience design services. CDL also manages all the licenses for consortial purchases. It has put a lot of effort into developing services and resources to support and advocate for OA.

Appendix 3 Critical information in deciding to support OA

Critical information in deciding to support OA (detailed data). The respondents answered the question: 'How might the following factors [see the chart legend] influence you/your institution's decision to support such an infrastructure. In the chart in the report, in order to increase readability, 'Much more likely to support' was merged with 'Slightly more likely to support'

	If the infrastructure is commercial		If the infrastructure is non-commercial		If the infrastructure is developed according to the principles of the Open Source		If your institution has ownership/control over the infrastructure		If your institution has control over which specific projects/publishers you support		If access to specific projects/publishers is determined via a centralised platform		If the infrastructure is community led or governed		If the infrastructure has publicly available/transparent governance	
	<i>UK</i>	<i>US</i>	<i>UK</i>	<i>US</i>	<i>UK</i>	<i>US</i>	<i>UK</i>	<i>US</i>	<i>UK</i>	<i>US</i>	<i>UK</i>	<i>US</i>	<i>UK</i>	<i>US</i>	<i>UK</i>	<i>US</i>
Much more likely to support	0	0	2	6	6	7	4	4	4	8	0	2	6	9	10	13
Slightly more likely to support	0	0	8	13	6	9	4	10	4	10	8	8	8	9	4	7
Neither more nor less likely to support	8	7	4	3	2	6	8	8	8	4	6	8	2	3	0	2
Slightly less likely to support	8	8	2	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	3	0	1	0	0

Much less likely to support	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0
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